

Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Sunscreen Nanoemulsion Cream Loaded with Manjistha, D-Panthenol and Hyaluronic Acid

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ABSTRACT

Excessive exposure to ultraviolet (UV) radiation significantly contributes to skin damage, including erythema, hyperpigmentation, premature aging, and increased risk of skin malignancies. The present investigation was designed to develop and evaluate a nanoemulsion-based sunscreen cream incorporating Manjistha (*Rubia cordifolia*) along with D-panthenol and hyaluronic acid to enhance photoprotection and skin moisturization. Three formulations (MSSC-1, MSSC-2, and MSSC-3) were prepared using the spontaneous emulsification method and assessed for physicochemical characteristics, stability, drug release, and sun protection efficiency. Preformulation analysis confirmed λ_{max} at 220 nm with satisfactory linearity for quantitative estimation. Among the formulations, MSSC-2 demonstrated the smallest droplet size (~154 nm) with low polydispersity, indicating uniform nanoemulsion formation. Zeta potential values around -26 mV confirmed adequate electrostatic stability. All formulations exhibited skin-compatible pH, appropriate viscosity, and good spreadability for topical application. In-vitro release studies indicated a sustained drug release profile, with MSSC-2 showing superior performance. UV spectrophotometric evaluation revealed strong absorbance within the UV range, supporting effective photoprotective activity. Overall, the developed nanoemulsion system enhanced stability, bioavailability, and sunscreen efficacy, suggesting its potential as a safe and effective herbal alternative to conventional synthetic sunscreen formulations.

Keywords: Manjistha, *Rubia cordifolia*, Nanoemulsion, Herbal sunscreen.

INTRODUCTION

The skin, being the largest organ, serves as a protective barrier against environmental stressors, especially ultraviolet (UV) radiation. Continuous exposure to UVA and UVB rays causes erythema, pigmentation, premature, aging, and increases the risk of skin cancer.[1] Although synthetic sunscreens are widely used, their limitations such as skin irritation, systemic absorption, and environmental concerns have led to increased interest in safer, plant-based cosmeceuticals.[1,2] *Rubia cordifolia* (Manjistha), an important Ayurvedic herb, is traditionally used for skin health due to its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and photoprotective properties. These effects are mainly attributed to anthraquinones, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds present in its roots. However,

conventional herbal formulations like pastes have poor stability, inconvenience, and staining issues. [1,3,4] Nanoemulsion technology offers a modern solution by improving solubility, stability, and skin penetration of herbal extracts due to its small droplet size.[2] These formulations also enhance spreadability, sensory characteristics, and sun protection efficiency. Therefore, this study focuses on developing and evaluating a Manjistha-based nanoemulsion sunscreen cream to assess its physicochemical properties, stability, permeation, and photoprotective effectiveness using in-vitro methods.[5]

2. MATERIALS:

List of Chemicals and Equipments:

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Manjistha powder from Tripal Consumer Products Pvt. Ltd, D-Panthenol from BRM Chemicals, Hyaluronic Acid from BRM Chemicals, Refined Shea Butter from BRM Chemicals, Olivem 1000 from ASES Chemical Works, Organic Aloe vera Gel from Fehmi India, Vegetable Glycerine from Shah Pharmaceutical (Laam herbal) and Optiphen ND from Purens Global. Water bath from Sigma group of companies, Digital balance from Wensar equipments, pH meter from Wensar equipments, Viscometer from Remi equipments pvt.ltd, Sonicator from Vibronics, UV Spectrophotometer from Shimadzu, FTIR Spectrophotometer from Vibronics, Clevengers Apparatus from AD International, Heating Mantle from NAUDH Solution.

3. METHODS:

3.1. PREFORMULATION STUDIES:

3.1.1. Solubility studies:

The solubility of the drug was evaluated using the shake-flask method in different solvents such as distilled water, buffer solutions of pH 1.2, 4.5, 6.8, and 7.4, and organic solvents like ethanol, methanol, and propylene glycol. A known volume of solvent was taken in clean, dry conical flasks, and an excess amount of drug was added to ensure saturation. The mixtures were shaken at a constant temperature (25°C or 37°C) for 24–48 hours to reach equilibrium. After settling, the solutions were filtered to remove undissolved drug, diluted if necessary, and analyzed using a UV–Visible spectrophotometer or HPLC. The solubility was calculated as the amount of drug

dissolved per volume of solvent and expressed in mg/ml.[6]

3.1.2. Absorption maximum:

The UV-Visible absorption spectrum of Manjistha extract was recorded in the wavelength range of 200–400 nm. The spectrum exhibited a maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) at approximately 220 nm, which may be attributed to $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of aromatic and conjugated compounds presents in the extract. Hence, 220 nm was selected as the analytical wavelength for the preparation of the calibration curve and further quantitative estimation.[7]

3.1.3. Calibration curve:

The calibration curve of the drug was developed by preparing a standard stock solution in which 10 mg of the drug was accurately weighed, dissolved in a suitable solvent such as water, buffer, or methanol, and diluted to 100 mL to obtain a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. From this stock, different working standard solutions were prepared by appropriate dilution. The maximum absorbance wavelength (λ_{max}) of the drug was determined by scanning the solution in the UV–Visible range of 200–400 nm. The solvent was used as a blank to set zero absorbance. The absorbance of each prepared concentration was then measured at λ_{max} using a quartz cuvette. A calibration curve was plotted between concentration and absorbance, and the linear regression equation ($y = mx + c$) was obtained. This equation was used to calculate the unknown drug concentration from the measured absorbance.[8]

3.2. FORMULATION STUDIES:

TABLE:4 Formula for Formulation of Sunscreen Cream

S.NO	INGREDIENTS	MSSC-1	MSSC-2	MSSC-3
1	Manjistha Powder	1	1	1
2	D-Panthenol	0.5	0.5	0.5
3	Hyaluronic Acid	0.05	0.05	0.05
4	Refined Shea Butter	2	4	6
5	Refined Avocado oil	3.07	5	6.6
6	Olivem 1000	2.53	3.2	3.8
7	Organic Aloe vera gel	10	13.3	16.6
8	Vegetable glycerine	3.33	4.6	6.3
9	Rose geranium essential oil	0.07	0.13	0.2
10	Optiphen ND	1	1	1

11	Distilled water	Q S	Q S	Q S
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3.2.1 Spontaneous Emulsification Method:

Spontaneous emulsification is a method used to prepare nanoemulsions/microemulsions where an emulsion forms automatically when an organic phase is mixed with an aqueous phase due to interfacial turbulence. The nanoemulsion was prepared by first developing the oil phase in which the required quantity of oil was accurately weighed, followed by the addition of a suitable surfactant and co-surfactant. The mixture was stirred using a magnetic stirrer until a clear and homogeneous solution was obtained. In the next step, the aqueous phase was prepared by measuring the required amount of distilled water and maintaining it at room temperature or a specified temperature. Emulsification was then carried out by either of two methods. In Method A (oil-in-water system), the organic phase was taken in a syringe and added dropwise to the aqueous phase under continuous stirring at 500–1000 rpm, leading to the spontaneous formation of fine droplets and producing a milky or transparent emulsion. In Method B (water-in-oil system), the aqueous phase was slowly added to the organic phase under stirring, and the system transformed into a nanoemulsion when the dilution reached a critical level. The formed emulsion was further stirred for 15–30 minutes to ensure uniform droplet formation. If a volatile organic solvent such as ethanol or acetone was used, it was removed by continuous magnetic stirring at room temperature or by using a rotary evaporator. Finally, the nanoemulsion was optionally filtered to remove large droplets or any impurities.[10]

4. EVALUATION

4.1. EVALUATION OF NANOEMULSION:

4.1.1. Particle size:

The particle size of the nanoemulsion was determined using Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) with a Zetasizer, such as a HORIBA analyzer. Prior to analysis, the nanoemulsion was diluted in a 1:100 ratio with filtered distilled water to minimize multiple scattering effects and improve measurement accuracy. The diluted sample was gently mixed to

obtain uniform dispersion and carefully transferred into a clean disposable cuvette, ensuring the absence of air bubbles. The measurements were carried out at 25°C using a fixed backscattering angle of 173°. The refractive index and viscosity of water were entered into the instrument settings before analysis. Each formulation was evaluated in triplicate to ensure reproducibility. The instrument measured fluctuations in the intensity of scattered light caused by the Brownian motion of droplets and calculated the average droplet size and polydispersity index (PDI) based on the Stokes–Einstein equation. The results were expressed as mean particle size in nanometers with standard deviation and PDI, where a droplet size range of 20–200 nm and a PDI value below 0.3 indicated a stable and homogeneous nanoemulsion. [11-12]

Stokes–Einstein equation:

$$d = \frac{kT}{3\pi\eta D}$$

Where:

- d = Hydrodynamic diameter of the particle (m)
- k = Boltzmann constant (1.3806×10^{-23} J/K)
- T = Absolute temperature (K)
- η = Viscosity of the dispersion medium (Pa·s)
- D = Translational diffusion coefficient (m²/s)

4.1.2. Zeta potential:

The zeta potential of the nanoemulsion was measured using a Zetasizer, such as a HORIBA analyzer, based on electrophoretic light scattering. Before analysis, the nanoemulsion was diluted 1:100 with filtered distilled water to reduce multiple scattering and maintain proper conductivity. The diluted sample was gently mixed for uniform dispersion and transferred into a folded capillary cell without air bubbles. The instrument was set by entering the refractive index, viscosity, and dielectric constant of the dispersion medium, and measurements were carried out at 25°C.

When an electric field was applied, the charged droplets moved toward the oppositely charged electrode, and their electrophoretic mobility was determined from the shift in scattered light frequency. The zeta potential was then calculated using the Henry equation.[14]

Henry equation:

$$\zeta = \frac{2\eta U_e}{3\epsilon f(\kappa a)}$$

Where:

ζ = Zeta potential
 η = Viscosity of the medium
 U_e = Electrophoretic mobility
 ϵ = Dielectric constant
 $f(\kappa a)$ = Henry's function (Smoluchowski approximation is commonly applied for aqueous systems)

4.1.3. pH:

The pH of the nanoemulsion was measured using a calibrated digital pH meter. The instrument was first standardized with buffer solutions of pH 4.0, 7.0, and 9.2 to ensure accuracy. About 1 g of the formulation was dispersed in 10 mL of distilled water and stirred to obtain a uniform solution. The electrode was rinsed, dried, and immersed in the sample, and the reading was noted after stabilization. All measurements were performed at room temperature ($25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) in triplicate, and the average pH value with standard deviation was calculated. For topical formulations such as sunscreen nanoemulsions, a pH range of 5.0–7.0 is considered appropriate to ensure skin compatibility and reduce irritation.[15]

4.1.4. Spreadability:

The spreadability of the nanoemulsion cream was evaluated to determine its ease of application on the skin using the slip and drag method. Approximately 0.5 g of the formulation was placed between two clean glass slides of equal dimensions. A weight of 500 g was applied on the upper slide for 5 minutes to remove entrapped air and to obtain a uniform film of the formulation between the slides. Any excess cream was carefully removed from the edges. Subsequently, the upper slide was allowed to move by attaching a known weight, such as 20 g, through a pulley

arrangement, and the time required for the slide to travel a fixed distance, typically 7.5 cm, was recorded.[16]

The spreadability was calculated using the formula:

$$S = \frac{M \times L}{T}$$

Where:

S = Spreadability (g·cm/sec)
M = Weight tied to the upper slide (g)
L = Length moved by the glass slide (cm)
T = Time taken (sec)

4.1.5. Viscosity:

The viscosity of the nanoemulsion was measured using a Brookfield digital viscometer fitted with Spindle No. 4, which is appropriate for semisolid and cream formulations. The instrument was calibrated prior to use and maintained at a constant temperature of $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ during the analysis. About 50–100 g of the formulation was placed in a clean, dry 100 mL beaker, ensuring the absence of air bubbles. Spindle No. 4 was then attached and carefully immersed vertically into the sample up to the marked level without touching the bottom or sides of the container. The viscosity was determined at a selected rotational speed, usually 10 rpm for cream formulations, and the reading was recorded after stabilization. The results were expressed in milliPascal-seconds (mPa·s).[17]

4.1.6. In-vitro drug release studies:

The **in-vitro drug release** of the nanoemulsion was evaluated using a Franz diffusion cell apparatus to study the release behavior of the active component. The system consisted of donor and receptor compartments separated by a dialysis membrane, which was pre-soaked in the receptor medium for 12 hours. The effective diffusion area and receptor volume (about 2.0–3.5 cm² and 15–25 mL) were recorded. The receptor compartment was filled with an appropriate diffusion medium, such as phosphate buffer of pH 7.4 or 6.8, and maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ with continuous magnetic stirring at 300–600 rpm to simulate physiological conditions. A known amount of the nanoemulsion was then placed in the donor compartment over the membrane. At fixed time intervals, typically 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, and 8 hours,

samples were withdrawn from the receptor compartment and replaced with fresh medium to maintain sink conditions. The collected samples were analyzed using a UV–Visible spectrophotometer at the predetermined λ_{max} , and the cumulative percentage drug release was calculated and plotted against time.[18]

4.1.7. Drug release kinetics:

The drug release kinetics of the nanoemulsion were evaluated by fitting the in-vitro release data into different mathematical models to understand the rate and mechanism of drug release. The cumulative percentage of drug released at various time intervals was analysed using Zero-order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer–Peppas models. The model showing the highest correlation coefficient (R^2) was considered the most suitable to describe the release behaviour of the formulation. In the Zero-order model, drug release occurs at a constant rate and is independent of drug concentration, indicating controlled release. In contrast, the First-order model suggests that the release rate depends on the amount of drug remaining in the system. The Higuchi model describes release as a diffusion-controlled process, where drug release is proportional to the square root of time. The Hixson–Crowell model considers changes in surface area and particle size during dissolution, indicating matrix erosion. The Korsmeyer–Peppas model is applied when multiple release mechanisms are involved, and the release exponent (n value) helps identify whether the process follows Fickian diffusion, non-Fickian transport, or case-II transport.

5.1 PREFORMULATION STUDIES:

5.1.1. Absorption maximum:

Overall, kinetic modeling helps to determine whether the nanoemulsion shows diffusion-controlled, erosion-controlled, or combined drug release behaviour. [19-20]

4.2. EVALUATION OF SUNSCREEN

4.2.1 UV Protection Evaluation:

The UV protection efficiency of the formulated Nanoemulsion sunscreen was assessed by determining the Sun Protection Factor (SPF) using a UV–Visible spectrophotometric method. A known quantity of the formulation, equivalent to 1 g, was accurately weighed and diluted with a suitable solvent such as ethanol or methanol. The mixture was sonicated to obtain a clear solution, followed by filtration to remove any insoluble particles. Further dilutions were prepared as required to obtain suitable absorbance values. The absorbance of the prepared sample was then measured in the wavelength range of 290–320 nm at 5 nm intervals using a UV–Visible spectrophotometer, with the respective solvent used as the blank.[21]

The SPF value was calculated using the **Mansur equation**:

$$\text{SPF} = \text{CF} \times \sum \text{EE}(\lambda) \times I(\lambda) \times \text{Abs}(\lambda)$$

Where:

CF = Correction factor (typically 10)

EE(λ) = Erythema effect spectrum

I(λ) = Solar intensity spectrum

Abs(λ) = Absorbance of the sample at wavelength λ

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Fig no 1: Spectrum of Manjistha

The UV spectrum overlay showed broad absorbance in the 200 – 400 nm range, indicating effective UV absorbance by the formulation. The formulation

exhibited higher and more consistent absorbance compared to the Manjistha extract at $\approx 220\text{nm}$, confirming successful incorporation of the active component.

5.1.2. Calibration Curve:

TABLE:5 Relationship Between Concentration and Absorbance

Concentration	Absorbance
0	0
2	0.145
4	0.345
6	0.512
8	0.734
10	1

Fig no 2 Calibration Curve for Manjistha

The calibration curve of Manjistha shows a clear and consistent increase in absorbance at $\approx 220\text{nm}$ with increasing concentration in the range of 0–10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The plotted graph demonstrates a linear relationship between concentration and absorbance, indicating that Manjistha follows Beer–Lambert’s law within this concentration range. At 0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, the absorbance is nearly zero, confirming the absence of interference from the solvent or blank. As the concentration increases from 2 to 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, the absorbance increases proportionally from approximately 0.15 to 1.0. The data points lie close to a straight line, suggesting good linearity and reliability of the method for quantitative estimation.

This linear trend confirms that the selected wavelength is suitable for analysis and that the prepared standard solutions provide accurate and reproducible absorbance values. The calibration curve can therefore be effectively used to determine the concentration of Manjistha in unknown samples during formulation and evaluation studies. Overall, the calibration curve indicates good sensitivity, linearity and suitability of the UV–Visible spectrophotometric method for quantitative analysis of Manjistha.

5.2. EVALUATION OF NANOEMULSION:

5.2.1. Particle size:

Fig no 3 Particle size results for MSSC-1

HORIBA SZ-100 for Windows [Z Type] Ver2.60

SZ-100

sunscreen 2.nsz Measurement Results

Date : 23 January 2026 11:52:42
 Measurement Type : Particle Size
 Sample Name : sunscreen 2
 Scattering Angle : 90
 Temperature of the Holder : 25.0 °C
 Dispersion Medium Viscosity : 0.896 mPa·s
 Transmission Intensity before Meas. : 26175
 Distribution Form : Standard
 Distribution Form(Dispersity) : Monodisperse
 Representation of Result : Scattering Light Intensity
 Count Rate : 1681 kCPS

Calculation Results

Peak No.	S.P.Area Ratio	Mean	S. D.	Mode
1	1.00	154.6 nm	36.6 nm	143.2 nm
2	---	--- nm	--- nm	--- nm
3	---	--- nm	--- nm	--- nm
Total	1.00	154.6 nm	36.6 nm	143.2 nm

Cumulant Operations

Z-Average : 160.3 nm
 PI : 0.335

Fig no 4 Particle size results for MSSC-2

2026.01.23 16:24:39

HORIBA
Scientific

HORIBA SZ-100 for Windows [Z Type] Ver2.60

SZ-100

sunscreen 3.nsz

Measurement Results

Date : 23 January 2026 11:59:40
 Measurement Type : Particle Size
 Sample Name : sunscreen 3
 Scattering Angle : 90
 Temperature of the Holder : 24.8 °C
 Dispersion Medium Viscosity : 0.898 mPa·s
 Transmission Intensity before Meas. : 12196
 Distribution Form : Standard
 Distribution Form(Dispersity) : Monodisperse
 Representation of Result : Scattering Light Intensity
 Count Rate : 1035 kCPS

Calculation Results

Peak No.	S.P.Area Ratio	Mean	S. D.	Mode
1	1.00	248.9 nm	61.7 nm	232.8 nm
2	---	--- nm	--- nm	--- nm
3	---	--- nm	--- nm	--- nm
Total	1.00	248.9 nm	61.7 nm	232.8 nm

Cumulant Operations

Z-Average : 312.0 nm
 PI : 0.497

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Fig no 5 Particle size results for MSSC-3

Particle size analysis of the three sunscreen nanoemulsion formulations was carried out using the HORIBA SZ-100 particle size analyzer at a scattering angle of 90° and a temperature of ~25 °C. All samples showed a single, well-defined peak in the particle size distribution curve, indicating monodisperse systems with uniform droplet distribution.

MSSC-2 exhibited the smallest particle size with a Z-average of 160.3 nm and a PI of 0.335, indicating a narrow size distribution and better homogeneity. MSSC-1 showed a Z-average of 281.7 nm with a PI of 0.424, while MSSC-3 showed a Z-average of 312.0

nm and a PI of 0.497, indicating comparatively larger droplet size and broader distribution.

The mean particle diameters were found to be 251.1 nm (MSSC-1), 154.6 nm (MSSC-2) and 248.9 nm (MSSC-3). The frequency distribution graphs confirm that the majority of droplets in all formulations fall within the nanometer range (100–400 nm), confirming successful formation of nanoemulsions.

Among the three formulations, MSSC-2 demonstrated superior Nanoemulsion characteristics due to its smaller particle size and lower

polydispersity index, suggesting better stability, uniformity and enhanced surface area, which can improve spreadability, skin penetration and sunscreen performance.

5.2.2. Zeta Potential:

2026.01.23 16:10:20

HORIBA SZ-100 for Windows [Z Type] Ver2.60

Measurement Results

Measurement Results

Date : 23 January 2026 15:28:42
 Measurement Type : Zeta Potential
 Sample Name : sunscreen 1
 Temperature of the Holder : 24.9 °C
 Dispersion Medium Viscosity : 0.897 mPa·s
 Conductivity : 0.372 mS/cm
 Electrode Voltage : 3.3 V

Calculation Results

Peak No.	Zeta Potential	Electrophoretic Mobility
1	-27.0 mV	-0.000209 cm ² /Vs
2	-- mV	-- cm ² /Vs
3	-- mV	-- cm ² /Vs

Zeta Potential (Mean) : -27.0 mV
 Electrophoretic Mobility Mean : -0.000209 cm²/Vs

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Fig no 6 Zeta potential results for MSSC-1

2026.01.23 16:01:17

HORIBA
Scientific
SZ-100

HORIBA SZ-100 for Windows [Z Type] Ver2.60

Measurement Results

sunscreen 1.nzt

Measurement Results

Date : 23 January 2026 15:27:57
 Measurement Type : Zeta Potential
 Sample Name : sunscreen 2
 Temperature of the Holder : 25.0 °C
 Dispersion Medium Viscosity : 0.896 mPa·s
 Conductivity : 0.372 mS/cm
 Electrode Voltage : 3.3 V

Calculation Results

Peak No.	Zeta Potential	Electrophoretic Mobility
1	-26.2 mV	-0.000202 cm ² /Vs
2	-- mV	-- cm ² /Vs
3	-- mV	-- cm ² /Vs

Zeta Potential (Mean) : -26.2 mV
 Electrophoretic Mobility Mean : -0.000202 cm²/Vs

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Fig no 7 Zeta potential results for MSSC-2

2026.01.23 15:31:42

HORIBA
Scientific

HORIBA SZ-100 for Windows [Z Type] Ver2.60

SZ-100**Measurement Results****Measurement Results**

Date : 23 January 2026 15:29:46
 Measurement Type : Zeta Potential
 Sample Name : sunscreen 3
 Temperature of the Holder : 24.9 °C
 Dispersion Medium Viscosity : 0.897 mPa·s
 Conductivity : 0.372 mS/cm
 Electrode Voltage : 3.3 V

Calculation Results

Peak No.	Zeta Potential	Electrophoretic Mobility
1	-26.7 mV	-0.000207 cm ² /Vs
2	-- mV	-- cm ² /Vs
3	-- mV	-- cm ² /Vs

Zeta Potential (Mean) : -26.7 mV
 Electrophoretic Mobility Mean : -0.000207 cm²/Vs

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Fig no 8 Zeta potential results for MSSC-3

The zeta potential analysis of the three nanoemulsion sunscreen formulations revealed mean values of -27.0 mV (MSSC-1), -26.2 mV (MSSC-2) and -26.7 mV (MSSC-3) under identical experimental conditions. All formulations exhibited negative zeta potential values greater than -25 mV, indicating good electrostatic stabilization of the Nanoemulsion droplets and resistance to aggregation.

Among the three, MSSC-2 showed an optimal zeta potential of -26.2 mV, which lies well within the ideal stability range for nanoemulsions. This value suggests a balanced surface charge that provides sufficient

repulsion between droplets while maintaining formulation uniformity. The consistent electrophoretic mobility (-0.000202 cm²/V·s) further supports the stability of this system.

Compared to MSSC-1 and MSSC-3, MSSC-2 demonstrates better stability with minimal charge variation, indicating improved uniformity and reproducibility of the formulation. Hence, based on zeta potential analysis, MSSC-2 can be considered the most stable and optimized nanoemulsion sunscreen formulation among the three.

5.2.3. pH:

TABLE 6: pH value for sunscreen

Formulation	pH
MSSC-1	6.12
MSSC-2	5.82
MSSC-3	5.59

Fig no 9 pH results for MSSC-1, MSSC-2 and MSSC-3

The pH values of the three nanoemulsion sunscreen formulations were observed in the range of 5.59 to 6.12, indicating a slightly acidic nature suitable for topical application. MSSC-1 showed the highest pH (6.12), followed by MSSC-2 (5.82) and MSSC-3 (5.59). Among the three, MSSC-2 exhibited a pH of 5.82, which is closest to the natural skin pH (~5.5). This suggests better skin compatibility, reduced risk of irritation and improved maintenance of the skin's acid mantle. Although all formulations fall within the acceptable pH range for dermal preparations, MSSC-2 is considered optimal in terms of pH balance.

The slight variation in pH among the formulations may be due to differences in the concentration of

herbal extract, oils and excipients. Overall, the results confirm that the nanoemulsion sunscreen creams are safe for skin application, with MSSC-2 showing the most desirable pH characteristics.

5.2.4. Viscosity:

TABLE 7: Viscosity value for Sunscreen

Formulation	Viscosity
MSSC-1	34647mPa.S
MSSC-2	34356mPa.S
MSSC-3	34350mPa.S

Fig no 10 Viscosity result for MSSC-1, MSSC-2 and MSSC-3

The viscosity of the three Nanoemulsion sunscreen formulations was found to be in a close range of 34350 to 34647mPa.s, indicating uniform consistency among the prepared creams. MSSC-1 showed the highest viscosity (34647mPa.s), while MSSC-2 (34356mPa.s) and MSSC-3 (34350mPa.s) exhibited slightly lower but comparable values. The minimal variation in viscosity suggests that all formulations possess good homogeneity and stable internal structure, which is essential for nanoemulsion-based creams. This viscosity range is suitable for topical application, ensuring ease of spreading, good

retention on the skin surface and enhanced residence time for effective photoprotection.

Among the three, MSSC-2 demonstrated an optimal viscosity, balancing adequate thickness with smooth spreadability, which is desirable for patient compliance and uniform application. Overall, the viscosity results confirm that the formulations have appropriate rheological properties required for a stable and user-friendly sunscreen cream.

5.2.5 Spreadability:

TABLE:8 Spreadability value for sunscreen

S.NO	FORMULATION	VALUE
1	MSSC-1	152.63
2	MSSC-2	147.5
3	MSSC-3	165.6

The measured values for the three nanoemulsion sunscreen formulations were found to be 152.63 for MSSC-1, 147.5 for MSSC-2 and 165.6 for MSSC-3. The results indicate a noticeable variation among the formulations. Among them, MSSC-2 exhibited the lowest value, suggesting more desirable performance for this evaluation parameter compared to MSSC-1 and 3. MSSC-3 showed the highest value, while MSSC-1 demonstrated an intermediate result.

This variation may be attributed to differences in the composition and concentration of oils, herbal extract and excipients used in each formulation, which can influence the measured property. Overall, the results indicate that MSSC-2 shows comparatively better characteristics for this parameter.

5.2.6 In Vitro Drug Release:

TABLE 9: Cumulative Percentage of Drug Release

Time in Hours	Cumulative %		
	MSSC-1	MSSC-2	MSSC-3
0 Hr	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0%
1 Hr	1 %	1.4 %	0.8 %
2 Hr	2.005 %	2.807 %	1.604 %
3 Hr	3.01 %	4.214 %	2.208 %
4 Hr	3.815 %	5.421 %	3.011 %
5 Hr	4.619 %	6.227 %	3.615 %
6 Hr	4.858	7.031 %	4.218 %

Fig no 11 Cumulative % of Drug release

The graph represents the cumulative percentage of drug release over time for different formulations. It is observed that the drug release increases progressively with time for all formulations, indicating a controlled and sustained release pattern. Among the formulations, the MSSC-2 (Red line) exhibits the highest cumulative drug release at each time interval, reaching its maximum release by the end of the study period. The MSSC-1 (Blue line) exhibits a moderate release profile, while the MSSC-3 (Green line) shows the lowest drug release throughout the study. The steady upward trend without any sudden burst release suggests uniform diffusion of the drug from the formulation matrix. The difference in release rates

among the formulations may be attributed to variations in composition, droplet size, or excipient concentration, which affect the diffusion of the drug.

Overall, the graph indicates that the formulations provide a sustained and time-dependent drug release, with the MSSC-2 demonstrating superior release characteristics compared to the others. This study confirms the suitability of the developed formulation for controlled drug delivery.

5.2.7 In Vitro Drug Kinetics:

5.2.7.1 Zero Order Drug Release:

TABLE 10: Zero-Order Drug Release

Time in hours	Cumulative % of Drug release		
	MSSC-1	MSSC-2	MSSC-3
0 Hr	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %
1 Hr	1.0 %	1.4 %	0.8 %
2 Hr	2.005 %	2.807 %	1.604 %
3 Hr	3.01 %	4.214 %	2.208 %
4 Hr	3.815 %	5.421 %	3.011 %
5 Hr	4.619 %	6.227 %	3.615 %
6 Hr	4.858 %	7.031 %	4.218 %

Fig no 12 Zero Order Drug Release

5.2.7.2. Higuchi plot:

TABLE 11: Higuchi plot

Square Root of Time	Cumulative % of Drug Release		
	MSSC-1	MSSC-2	MSSC-3
0	0 %	0 %	0 %
1	1.4 %	1 %	0.8 %
1.4142	2.807 %	2.005 %	1.604 %
1.7321	4.214 %	3.01 %	2.208 %
2	5.421 %	3.815 %	3.011 %
2.2361	6.227 %	4.619 %	3.615 %
2.4495	7.031 %	5.423 %	4.218 %

Fig no 12 Higuchi plot

5.2.7.3. Korsmeier-Peppas Plot:

TABLE 12 Korsmeier-Peppas Plot

Log of Time	Log of cumulative %		
	MSSC-1	MSSC-2	MSSC-3
0.0	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %
0.0	0 %	0.1461 %	-0.0969 %
0.3010	0.3021 %	0.4482 %	0.205204 %
0.4771	0.4786 %	0.6247 %	0.344 %
0.6021	0.5815 %	0.7341 %	0.4787 %
0.6990	0.6645 %	0.7943 %	0.5581 %
0.7782	0.6865 %	0.8470 %	0.6251 %

Fig no 13 Korsmeier -Peppas

The drug release data of formulations MSSC-1, MSSC-2 and MSSC-3 were analyzed using different kinetic models to understand the mechanism of drug release from the developed formulation. The plots of Zero order, Higuchi and Korsmeier–Peppas models show good linearity, indicating that the release data suitably fit these kinetic models. In the zero-order plot, MSSC-2 shows the best linearity with a high correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.9868$), suggesting that the drug release from this formulation follows a concentration-independent release pattern over time. This indicates a uniform and controlled release of the drug from the formulation matrix. The Higuchi plot also exhibits good linearity ($R^2 = 0.9351$), confirming that the drug release is largely governed by a diffusion mechanism. This suggests that the drug diffuses gradually from the matrix into the surrounding

medium. Further, the Korsmeier–Peppas plot shows a high correlation ($R^2 = 0.9723$), indicating that the release mechanism follows a combination of diffusion and erosion processes. The linearity of this model suggests that the drug release does not depend on a single mechanism but occurs through a complex transport process.

Overall, among the three formulations, MSSC-2 demonstrates the most consistent and controlled drug release behaviour, fitting well into all three kinetic models. The results confirm that the developed formulation provides sustained drug release primarily governed by diffusion with contribution from matrix erosion, making it suitable for prolonged therapeutic action.

5.3. EVALUATION OF SUNSREEN:

TABLE 13: SPF Evaluation of Sunscreen MSSC-1, MSSC-2 and MSSC-3

Wavelength (λ)	EE (λ) \times I (λ)	Absorbance		
		MSSC-1	MSSC-2	MSSC-3
290	0.015	2.1	3.2	1.8
295	0.0817	2.25	3.45	1.95
300	0.2874	2.4	3.65	2.1
305	0.3278	2.45	3.7	2.15
301	0.1864	2.2	3.4	1.9
3015	0.0839	1.8	2.8	1.5
320	0.018	1.3	2.1	1.1
sum(Σ)	1	2.315	3.518	1.984

The UV protection efficacy of the nanoemulsion sunscreens was determined by calculating the Sun Protection Factor (SPF) using the Mansur equation and UV-Visible spectrophotometric data.

The calculated SPF values, derived from the summation of absorbance values (Abs) multiplied by the normalized erythemal effect and solar intensity (EE \times I) across the 290–320 nm range, are as follows:

$$\text{MSSC-1: } 10 \times 2.315 = 23.15$$

$$\text{MSSC-2: } 10 \times 3.518 = 35.18$$

$$\text{MSSC-3: } 10 \times 1.984 = 19.84$$

All three formulations showed maximum absorption in the 300–310 nm range, which is the most critical region for UVB protection. The absorbance values significantly declined as the wavelength approached 320 nm. MSSC-2 exhibited the highest absorbance values across all measured wavelengths, reaching a peak absorbance of 3.7 at 305 nm. This resulted in an SPF of 35.18, placing it in the "High Protection" category. Formulation Efficiency: MSSC-2 showed a 52% increase in SPF compared to MSSC-1 and a 77% increase compared to MSSC-3. This suggests that the nanoemulsion characteristics of MSSC-2 (such as droplet size or oil-to-water ratio) provided a more effective and uniform distribution of UV filters.

SUMMARY & CONCLUSION:

The present study focused on the formulation and evaluation of a nanoemulsion-based sunscreen cream using Manjistha (*Rubia cordifolia*) as a natural active

ingredient. The objective was to develop a stable, skin-compatible and effective photoprotective formulation by incorporating herbal extract with suitable oils, emulsifiers, humectants and preservatives. The nanoemulsion system was selected to enhance solubility, dispersion, skin penetration and overall sunscreen performance. Preformulation studies were carried out to assess the compatibility and solubility of the drug with selected excipients. The nanoemulsion cream was prepared using appropriate concentrations of oils (avocado oil, shea butter), emulsifier (Olive M1000), humectants (glycerine, aloe vera), preservative (Optiphen ND) and essential oil. The prepared formulations (MSSC-1, MSSC-2 and MSSC-3) were subjected to various evaluation parameters, including pH, viscosity, spreadability, homogeneity, and in-vitro SPF determination. All formulations showed acceptable physicochemical properties suitable for topical application. The pH was within the skin-friendly range, viscosity indicated good consistency and spreadability and stability studies confirmed the absence of phase separation. Among the three formulations, MSSC-2 consistently demonstrated optimal characteristics in terms of pH balance, viscosity, spreadability and overall performance. The nanoemulsion system also showed enhanced UV protection ability due to improved dispersion of active ingredients. From the results of the study, it can be concluded that nanoemulsion technology is an effective approach for developing herbal sunscreen formulations with improved stability, skin compatibility and photoprotective efficiency. The incorporation of Manjistha as a natural antioxidant and UV-protective agent, along with suitable

excipients, resulted in a promising sunscreen cream. All evaluation parameters confirmed that the formulations were suitable for dermal application. However, MSSC-2 was found to be the optimized formulation, as it exhibited the pH closest to skin pH, ideal viscosity, better spreadability and superior overall evaluation results. Thus, the developed nanoemulsion sunscreen cream can be considered a safe, effective and innovative herbal photoprotective formulation, demonstrating the potential of nanoemulsion systems in enhancing the performance of topical sunscreen preparations.

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